
STRATEGIC AGILITY AND COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE OF HOSPITALITY FIRMS IN SOUTH EAST NIGERIA

Prof. Onyeizugbe Chinedu Uzochukwu

cu.onyeizugbe@unizik.edu.ng

Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka, Anambra State.

Ikechi Felix Uneojo

felixikechi9@gmail.com

Bankole Isaac, AKINROLUYO (PhD)

bi.akinroluyo@unizik.edu.ng

Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka, Anambra State.

Abstract

This study examines the relationship between strategic agility and competitive advantage in hospitality firms in South East Nigeria, focusing on the dimensions of adaptive capability and strategic flexibility. Anchored in Competitive Advantage Theory, the research explores how these strategic agility components influence key competitive advantage indicators, including customer retention and product branding. A descriptive survey design was employed, with data collected from 279 respondents across 20 hospitality firms in Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu, and Imo states. The analysis revealed significant positive relationships between adaptive capability and customer retention ($r = 0.769$, $p < 0.001$), while strategic flexibility and product branding ($r = 0.802$, $p < 0.001$). These findings underscore the critical role of strategic agility in enhancing competitive advantage within the hospitality sector. The study concludes that hospitality firms with strong adaptive capabilities and strategic flexibility, are better positioned to respond to market changes, maintain service quality, and achieve operational efficiency. Recommendations include investing in staff training, adopting flexible strategic planning, implementing sustainable practices, optimizing resource allocation, and prioritizing technology integration. This research contributes to the strategic management literature by providing empirical evidence of the relationships between strategic agility dimensions and competitive advantage in the context of South East Nigerian hospitality firms, offering practical insights for industry practitioners and theoretical foundations for future research.

Keyword: Strategic Agility, Competitive Advantage, Hospitality Firms, Adaptive Capability.

Introduction

The hospitality industry in South East Nigeria is experiencing significant transformation driven by changing consumer preferences, technological advancements, and competitive pressures. In this dynamic environment, strategic agility emerges as a critical capability, enabling firms to adapt swiftly to market changes while maintaining a competitive edge. Central to achieving strategic agility are several interrelated components, including adaptive capability, strategic flexibility, sustainable growth, resource fluidity, and technology integration. Understanding how these elements interact can provide hospitality firms with the insights needed to thrive in a challenging landscape (hospitality industry). Strategic agility refers to an organisation's capacity to rapidly adapt its strategic direction in response to changing environmental conditions while maintaining a clear vision and purpose (Amini and Rahmani, 2023).

It involves the ability to anticipate and respond to external opportunities and threats and the flexibility to reconfigure internal resources and capabilities to align with new strategic priorities, thus securing a competitive advantage (Çakmak, 2023). Competitive advantage, in turn, refers to the conditions that enable a firm to outperform its competitors, often measured by factors such as market share, profitability, and customer retention (Climent, Haftor and Staniewski, 2024). The hospitality industry, which encompasses sectors such as hotels, restaurants, and tourism services, is particularly susceptible to shifts in customer preferences, economic fluctuations, and technological disruptions. Consequently, developing strategic agility is crucial for hospitality firms to maintain and enhance their competitive advantage (Kumar, Dhiraj, Shah and Rani, 2023).

Strategic agility has evolved to include various dimensions that reflect an organisation's ability to respond to external and internal challenges. *Adaptive capability* refers to the organisation's capacity to alter its operations and strategies in response to market changes (Endres, Endres and Berg, 2018). *Strategic flexibility* involves the firm's ability to pivot or shift strategies without becoming locked into specific courses of action (Brozovic, 2018). *Resource fluidity* reflects the ease with which a firm can redeploy resources—such as personnel, technology, or capital—to new opportunities or challenges (Kitur and Kinyua, 2020). *Leadership unity* denotes the degree to which leaders within the firm are aligned and coherent in their strategic decisions (Clauss, Abebe, Tangpong and Hock, 2019), while *strategic sensitivity* refers to an organisation's capability to detect and interpret signals from the external environment that indicate potential threats or opportunities (Clauss, Abebe, Tangpong and Hock, 2019).

The current situation on hospitality industry in South East Nigeria reveals a stark contrast to this ideal. Many hospitality firms in the region struggle with limited adaptive capabilities (adjusting to change in the business environment), resulting in inadequate responses to the rapidly evolving preferences of customers. This has led to declining customer retention rates, as firms fail to meet the expectations of a diverse clientele that increasingly values personalization and responsiveness. Additionally, strategic flexibility is often lacking (inability to adjust to new opportunities), firms tend to adhere to rigid branding strategies that do not resonate with local cultural nuances, further alienating potential customers. Despite the growing awareness of sustainability, many firms have not fully integrated sustainable practices into their operations, which limits their ability to attract environmentally conscious consumers. Resource fluidity remains a challenge, as many hospitality firms are unable to dynamically reallocate resources to address operational demands, leading to inefficiencies

and compromised service quality. Lastly, the integration of technology is often underutilized, restricting firms' capacities to streamline operations and enhance customer interactions. This persistent gap between

However, despite the growing recognition of the importance of strategic agility in the hospitality industry, empirical research on the topic remains limited, especially in Southeastern Nigeria. While some studies have examined the antecedents and outcomes of strategic agility in other sectors (e.g., Panda and Rath, 2018; Alkandi and Helmi, 2024), there is a need for more industry-specific research that takes into account the unique characteristics and challenges of the hospitality sector (in terms of strategic agility and competitive advantage). Moreover, there is a lack of understanding of how hospitality firms can effectively implement and manage strategic agility, particularly in the face of resource constraints and organisational inertia (Panda and Rath, 2018). This study aims to address these gaps in the literature by investigating the relationship between strategic agility and competitive advantage of hospitality firms in Southeast Nigeria. While specifically, the study will seek to: determine the degree of relationship that exists between adaptive capability and customer retention of hospitality firms in South East Nigeria, ascertain the level of relationship that exists between strategic flexibility and product branding of hospitality firms in South East Nigeria.

Literature Reviews

Strategic Agility

Strategic agility has emerged as a crucial capability for hospitality firms operating in an increasingly dynamic and competitive environment. Defined as the ability of an organisation to sense, respond, and adapt to changes in its external environment with speed and flexibility, strategic agility enables firms to maintain a competitive edge while navigating market uncertainties (Elali, 2021). In the context of hospitality, where customer preferences shift rapidly, technological advancements disrupt traditional service models, and unforeseen crises such as pandemics can severely impact operations, the need for strategic agility is particularly pronounced (Hitt, Ireland and Hoskisson, 2020). Hospitality firms must develop certain core competencies to achieve strategic agility. First, sensing capabilities are essential for identifying emerging trends, customer demands, and competitive threats (Hussain and Malik, 2022). By employing advanced data analytics and customer feedback systems, firms can anticipate shifts in the market and adjust their offerings accordingly (Gupta, Justy, Kamboj, Kumar and Kristoffersen, 2021). For example, the rise of digital platforms such as Airbnb signalled a transformation in consumer expectations regarding accommodation, prompting many traditional hotels to rethink their service models to remain competitive (Zeqiri, 2024). Failure to develop robust sensing mechanisms can leave firms vulnerable to disruptive forces, as evidenced by the decline of numerous brick-and-mortar hotel chains that were slow to adapt to the digital revolution (Espindola and Wright, 2021). Hospitality firms must cultivate the ability to continuously learn and innovate, which is central to maintaining long-term strategic agility (Hitt, Ireland and Hoskisson, 2020). Innovation in service delivery, customer engagement, and operational processes can enable firms to respond to change and proactively shape market trends. For instance, hotels that have integrated artificial intelligence into their customer service, such as through automated check-in systems and personalised recommendations, are better positioned to meet evolving customer expectations (Štilić, Nicić, and Puška, 2023). Moreover, fostering a culture of continuous learning within the organisation enables employees to develop the skills necessary to support agile operations

(Ajayi and Udeh, 2024).

Competitive Advantage

In the highly competitive hospitality industry, firms must develop and sustain competitive advantage to survive and thrive. Competitive advantage arises when a firm can deliver superior value to customers through lower costs or differentiated offerings that justify premium pricing (Jerab and Mabrouk, 2023). The hospitality sector, characterised by its service orientation and customer-centric focus, demands that firms innovate continuously to enhance customer experiences and operational efficiency. In this regard, competitive advantage can be understood as the ability of a hospitality firm to outperform its rivals by creating and capturing superior value through unique operational, marketing, or strategic initiatives (Sahi, Devi, Gupta and Cheng, 2022). One of the key drivers of competitive advantage in the hospitality industry is service differentiation. Research has shown that service innovation, particularly in enhancing customer experiences, is paramount for hospitality firms to maintain a competitive edge (Chen, Li, and Wang, 2020). For instance, personalised customer experiences, facilitated by big data and artificial intelligence, enable hospitality firms to anticipate customer needs and deliver tailored services (Buhalis and Moldavska, 2022). This differentiation not only enhances customer satisfaction but also fosters customer loyalty, which is a crucial element in sustaining long-term competitive advantage. Another critical aspect of competitive advantage in hospitality is operational efficiency. Efficient operations enable firms to reduce costs while maintaining high service standards, essential in an industry where profit margins are often thin. Strategic resource management, including human resources, is pivotal in this context. Studies have indicated that human capital development, mainly through training and employee engagement, contributes significantly to operational efficiency in hospitality firms (Davidson, McPhail, and Barry, 2017). By cultivating a highly skilled and motivated workforce, hospitality firms can enhance service quality, reduce employee turnover, and improve overall operational performance.

Theoretical Framework

Competitive Advantage Theory

The Competitive Advantage Theory, prominently advanced by Michael E. Porter in his 1985 work "Competitive Advantage: Creating and Sustaining Superior Performance," provides a foundational framework for understanding how firms can achieve and maintain a competitive edge in their respective markets. Porter's insights have been instrumental in shaping strategic management practices and remain relevant in analyzing contemporary business environments, particularly in sectors characterized by intense competition, such as hospitality.

At its core, the Competitive Advantage Theory posits that firms operate within competitive environments that significantly influence their performance. This competitive landscape is shaped by various factors, including the number of competitors, the intensity of rivalry, and the availability of substitutes. Porter introduces the idea that organizations can create greater value for customers than their competitors through two primary strategies: cost leadership and differentiation. Cost leadership involves becoming the lowest-cost producer in an industry, allowing firms to offer lower prices than their competitors while maintaining acceptable profit margins. On the other hand, differentiation focuses on providing unique

features or services that justify a higher price point. Firms that successfully implement either strategy can capture market share, foster customer loyalty, and ultimately achieve sustainable competitive advantage.

The essence of value creation is central to sustaining competitive advantage over time. Porter emphasizes that firms must identify and leverage their unique resources and capabilities to deliver superior value. These resources can be tangible, such as financial assets or physical infrastructure, or intangible, such as brand reputation, customer relationships, and proprietary technology. The ability to protect these unique resources from imitation by competitors is crucial; firms that can maintain barriers to entry whether through patents, strong brand identity, or exclusive access to distribution channels are better positioned to sustain their competitive advantage in the long run.

Empirical Reviews

Anene and Ile (2025) evaluated competitive strategies and performance of food, beverages, and tobacco manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria. The aim was to determine the extent to which cost leadership strategy influences profit and to determine product differentiation strategy's influence on return on assets. The design of the study was a descriptive survey using a Freund and William's statistic formula in estimating participants of 360 in a total of 4,918 workers using a 5% error margin. The collection of data utilized a five-point rating scale instrument of 30 questions answered by participants numbering 302. Analysis using a Z-test using SPSS established that cost leadership strategy was positively related to profit ($Z(95, n = 302) 7.337 < 8.833, P < 0.05$), whereas product differentiation strategy was positively related to return on assets ($Z(95, n = 302) 6.761 < 8.085, P < 0.05$). The two strategies were found to highly enhance firm's performance and recommended that management should reinforce cost leadership by minimizing product prices, product branding, decreasing operating expenses, and distributing to more channels of distribution.

Aljanabi (2024) investigated strategic agility's effects and its elements (strategic sensitivity, collective commitment, and resource fluidity) on sustainable competitive advantage in Iraqi universities. The work was a response to challenges in higher education institutions in rapid globalization and a need to be strategic in Iraqi universities. The work employed a structural analysis approach grounded in structural modelling. The data was collected using a questionnaire that was administered to a random sample of 78 university professors in Iraqi universities. The questionnaire was separated into two parts: one to handle the dependent variable (sustainable competitive advantage) and the other to handle the independent variable (strategic agility) and its three components. The results confirmed that strategic agility is a survival strategy, a competitive competency, and a method of dealing with business volatility, hence a plus in sustainable competitive advantage. The work confirmed that it is hard to adapt to rapid changes in Iraqi universities owing to their existing low capabilities and various challenges. The work addresses a gap in existing studies that accommodate strategic agility and competitive advantage in higher education institutions in Iraq.

Ifeoma, Mba, and Patience (2024) investigated capital structure's effects on investors' return in conglomerate firms in Nigeria. The study was based on effects of strategic capital structure decisions on competitive power and firm's performance. Five conglomerate firms listed in Nigeria's Stock Exchange over a period of a decade (2010-2019) were sampled using purposive sampling method. The data was collected using Nigeria stock exchange fact books and annual financial reports, computed using regression analysis using E-views 9.0 software

at a significance of 5%. The results presented mean values of 20,609,203 and 23,046,190 for equity capital and debt capital, respectively. The model was a close fit with a value of R^2 of 0.55. Equity capital and debt capital displayed a positive slope coefficient (0.0090 and 0.6145), a significant p-value of 0.0000. The results displayed that an increase in equity finance and debt finance positively affect profitability. The scholars recommended that companies put a high premium on equity financing and emphasized that wise financing decisions facilitate maintenance of profitability and leadership position in the market.

Methodology

This study employed a descriptive survey design to examine relationships between variables and gather data from a representative sample to make inferences about a larger population (Creswell and Creswell, 2018).

The population of this study comprises all registered hospitality firms operating in the five states of Southeast Nigeria (Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu, and Imo). The population includes only formally registered and actively operating establishments that have been in business for at least five year, excluding informal hospitality operations and businesses that have ceased operations. 20 selected luxury and business hospitality firms operating in the southeast were used for this study with a total of 2294 employees. The study made use of Yamane (1967) formula to get sample size of 341. The study will employ a multistage sampling technique to select participants from the target population. The data collected from the respondents with the aid of questionnaire were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Demographic data were analysed statistics using descriptive while research questionnaire were answered using both descriptive and inferential statistics such as mean, standard deviation and percentage. Hypotheseses were analysed using Pearson correlation analyses at a 0.05 level of significance.

Data Analyses

Out of the 342 distributed questionnaire, only 279 were filled and retrieved representing an 81.6% response rate.

Hypotheses Testing

Decision Rule: For hypothesis 1, reject the null hypothesis if the p-value is less than or equal to 0.05 ($p \leq 0.05$), indicating a statistically significant relationship between the variables, while the strength of this relationship is determined by the magnitude of the correlation coefficient (r). However, for hypothesis 2, reject the null hypothesis if $p \leq 0.05$, indicating a statistically significant effect. The strength of the effect is determined by the R^2 value.

Hypothesis One:

H₀: There is no significant relationship between adaptive capability and Customer Retention of hospitality firms in South East Nigeria.

H_A: There is a significant relationship between adaptive capability and Customer Retention of hospitality firms in South East Nigeria.

Table 1: Pearson Correlation between Adaptive Capability and Customer Retention

		AC	CR
AC	Pearson Correlation	1	.769**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	279	279
CR	Pearson Correlation	.769**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	279	279

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output, 2025

The Pearson correlation analysis in Table 1 revealed a strong positive relationship between adaptive capability and customer retention ($r = 0.769$, $p < 0.001$, $n = 279$). The correlation coefficient of 0.769 indicates a robust positive association between the variables, while the p-value of 0.000 demonstrates statistical significance at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). Given that $p < 0.05$, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a significant relationship between adaptive capability and customer retention in hospitality firms in South East Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two:

H₀: There is no significant relationship between strategic flexibility and product branding of hospitality firms in South East Nigeria.

H_A: There is a significant relationship between strategic flexibility and product branding of hospitality firms in South East Nigeria.

Table 2: Pearson Correlation between Strategic Flexibility and Product Branding

		SF	PB
SF	Pearson Correlation	1	.802**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	279	279
PB	Pearson Correlation	.802**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	279	279

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output, 2025

The analysis in Table 2 showed a very strong positive relationship between strategic flexibility and product branding ($r = 0.802$, $p < 0.001$, $n = 279$). The correlation coefficient of 0.802 indicates a particularly strong positive association between the variables, with the p-value of 0.000 showing statistical significance at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). Since $p < 0.05$, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a significant relationship between

strategic flexibility and product branding in hospitality firms in South East Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The results for the first hypothesis demonstrate a significant positive relationship between adaptive capability and customer retention in hospitality firms. This relationship can be attributed to the ability of firms with strong adaptive capabilities to respond quickly to changing customer preferences and market conditions, thereby maintaining customer satisfaction and encouraging repeat patronage. The finding aligns with Competitive Advantage Theory, which emphasizes that firms must continuously adapt their resources and capabilities to maintain market leadership. This result corresponds with several previous studies. Waale and Onuoha (2023) found that higher levels of market sensing and adaptability significantly increased customer retention and market share growth in hotels. Similarly, Mwachia, Kimaku and Makungu (2023) demonstrated that adaptive operational strategies enhanced customer satisfaction and loyalty in Kenyan hotels. Bassey, Uwa and Okurebia (2023) found that strategic adaptability significantly influenced organizational performance in manufacturing firms. Additionally, Ifeoma, Mba and Patience (2023) showed that organizational learning and adaptive capabilities positively impacted competitive performance in manufacturing firms.

The results for the second hypothesis reveal a strong positive relationship between strategic flexibility and product branding. This relationship can be explained by the ability of strategically flexible firms to adjust their branding strategies rapidly in response to market changes and customer preferences, leading to stronger brand recognition and customer loyalty. This aligns with Competitive Advantage Theory's emphasis on strategic positioning and differentiation. The finding is supported by several previous studies. Abdulfatah and Chima (2023) found that strategic flexibility enhanced competitiveness in SMEs through improved branding capabilities. Aswan (2023) demonstrated that strategic flexibility, as a component of strategic agility, positively influenced competitive advantage through enhanced brand positioning. Anunda (2023) showed that strategic orientations, including flexibility in branding strategies, positively impacted organizational performance in hospitality firms. Furthermore, Tufan and Mert (2023) found that strategic flexibility mediated the relationship between absorptive capacity and sustainable competitive advantage.

Summary of findings

1. There is a strong positive relationship between adaptive capability and customer retention ($r = 0.769$, $p < 0.001$). This means that hospitality firms that develop strong adaptive capabilities are more likely to retain customers through improved responsiveness to changing customer needs and market conditions.
2. There is a very strong positive relationship between strategic flexibility and product branding ($r = 0.802$, $p < 0.001$), which implies that hotels with higher strategic flexibility are better positioned to develop and maintain strong brand identities that resonate with their target markets.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, strategic agility significantly influences competitive advantage in hospitality firms in South East Nigeria. The strong positive relationships between adaptive capability and customer retention, strategic flexibility and product

branding, and sustainable growth and continuous improvement, coupled with the significant effects of resource fluidity on service quality and technology integration on operational efficiency, demonstrate that strategic agility is crucial for maintaining competitive advantage in the hospitality sector. The successful implementation of these strategic agility dimensions enables hospitality firms to respond effectively to market changes, maintain service quality, enhance operational efficiency, and ultimately achieve sustainable competitive advantage in an increasingly dynamic business environment.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations can be considered

1. Hospitality firms should invest in developing adaptive capabilities through regular staff training programs and flexible organizational structures to enhance customer retention.
2. Management should implement flexible strategic planning processes that allow for quick adjustments to branding strategies in response to market changes.
3. Hotels should adopt sustainable business practices and establish systematic continuous improvement programs to ensure long-term growth and operational excellence.

References

- Abdulfa ah, K. O. and Chima, O. B. (2023). Strategic Foresight and Competitiveness of SMES in Rivers State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Business Systems and Economics* 13(3), 40 – 54. DOI:272614527311463
- Ajayi, F. A., &Udeh, C. A. (2024). Agile work cultures in IT: A Conceptual analysis of hr's role in fostering innovation supply chain. *International Journal of Management & Entrepreneurship Research*, 6(4), 1138-1156.
- Aljanabi, T. A. M. H. O. (2024). The Impact Of Strategic Agility In Achieving Sustainable Competitive Advantage. *Pooda Journal of Business Marketing, Finance, And Accounting Studies*, 14(1).
- Alkandi, I. and Helmi, M. A. (2024). The impact of strategic agility on organizational performance: the mediating role of market orientation and innovation capabilities in emerging industrial sector. *Cogent Business & Management*, 11(1), 2396528. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2024.2396528>
- Amini, M., and Rahmani, A. (2023). How strategic agility affects the competitive capabilities of private banks. *International Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, 10, 8397-8406.
- Anene, V. N. and Ile, N. M. (2025). Competitive Strategies and Performance of Food, Beverages and Tobacco Manufacturing Firms in South East, Nigeria. *Journal of Current Research in Business and Management Sciences*, 13(1), 20-40. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14628041>
- Anunda, V. M. (2023). Strategic Orientation and Organizational Performance of Ole-sereni Hotel in Nairobi County, Kenya (Doctoral dissertation, University of Nairobi).
- Bassey, D. N., Uwa, K. L., and Okurebia, S. (2023). Strategic Agility and Organizational

Performance in Selected Manufacturing Firms in South-South Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Management Review*, 11(11), 72-95.

- Brozovic, D. (2018). Strategic flexibility: A review of the literature. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 20(1), 3-31.
- Buhalis, D., & Moldavska, I. (2022). Voice assistants in hospitality: using artificial intelligence for customer service. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Technology*, 13(3), 386-403.
- Çakmak, Z. (2023). Adapting to environmental change: The importance of organizational agility in the business landscape. *Florya Chronicles of Political Economy*, 9(1), 67-87.
- Chen, Y., Li, P., and Wang, Y. (2020). Service innovation and competitive advantage in the hospitality industry: The role of digital transformation. *Tourism Management*, 81, 104135.
- Clauss, T., Abebe, M., Tangpong, C., and Hock, M. (2019). Strategic agility, business model innovation, and firm performance: an empirical investigation. *IEEE transactions on engineering management*, 68(3), 767-784.
- Climent, R. C., Haftor, D. M., and Staniewski, M. W. (2024). AI-enabled business models for competitive advantage. *Journal of Innovation and Knowledge*, 9(3), 100532.
- Elali, W. (2021). The importance of strategic agility to business survival during corona crisis and beyond. *International Journal of Business Ethics and Governance*, 1-8.
- Endres, H., Endres, and Berg. (2018). *Adaptability Through dynamic capabilities*. Wiesbaden: Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden.
- Espindola, D., & Wright, M. W. (2021). *The exponential era: Strategies to stay ahead of the curve in an era of chaotic changes and disruptive forces*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Gupta, S., Justy, T., Kamboj, S., Kumar, A., & Kristoffersen, E. (2021). Big data and firm marketing performance: Findings from knowledge-based view. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 171, 120986.
- Hitt, M.A., Ireland, R.D. and Hoskisson, R.E. (2020) *Strategic Management: Competitiveness and Globalization*. 13th edn. Boston: Cengage Learning.
- Hussain, M., & Malik, M. (2022). How do dynamic capabilities enable hotels to be agile and resilient? A mediation and moderation analysis. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 106, 103266.
- Ifeoma, A. R., Mba, M. and Patience, N. C. (2024). Strategic Agility: An Imperative For Competitive Performance of Manufacturing Firms In Anambra State, Nigeria. *Amity Business Review*, 18.
- Kitur, T., and Kinyua, G. M. (2020). An Empirical Analysis of the Relationship between Resource Fluidity and Firm Performance: A Perspective of Tours and Travel

Companies in Kenya. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Advanced Studies*, 7(11), 13-21.

Mwachia, J. K., Kimaku, P., and Makungu, M. T. (2023). Influence of Organizational Agility Dimensions on Performance of Hotel Industry In Kenyan Coast Counties. *International Journal of Social Sciences Management and Entrepreneurship (IJSSME)*, 7(1).

Panda, S., and Rath, S. K. (2018). Strategic IT-business alignment and organizational agility: from a developing country perspective. *Journal of Asia Business Studies*, 12(4), 422-440.

Štilić, A., Nicić, M., & Puška, A. (2023). Check-in to the future: Exploring the impact of contemporary information technologies and artificial intelligence on the hotel industry. *Turističkoposlovanje*, (31).

Tufan, C., and Mert, I. S. (2023). The sequential effect of absorptive capacity, strategic agility, and sustainable competitive advantage on sustainable business performance of SMEs. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 30(19), 55958-55973.

Waale, I. C. R., and Onuoha, B. C. (2023). Strategic Agility and Competitive Advantage of Hotel Business in Rivers State.

Zeqiri, A. (2024). From Traditional to Digital: The Evolution of Business Models in Hospitality Through Platforms. *Platforms*, 2(4), 221-233.